

INVESTMENT USING CRYPTOCURRENCY FOR A MACHINE LEARNING BASED STOCK PREDICTION MODEL

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Manuscript History

Number: IRJCS/RS/Vol.07/Issue05/MYCS10092

Received: 02, May 2020

Final Correction: 19, May 2020

Final Accepted: 27, May 2020

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26562/irjcs.2020.v0705.003>

Published: May 2020

Citation: Swastik, Dr. Murali (2020).. Investment using Cryptocurrency for a Machine Learning Based stock prediction Model. International Research Journal of Computer Science (IRJCS), Volume VII, 78-110.

Editor: Dr. A. Arul Lawrence selvakumar, Chief Editor, IRJCS, AM Publications, India

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I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. OBJECTIVE:

With this product, my objective was to make cryptocurrency investments simple & profitable. This product operates via an easy to use website allowing customers to buy, sell, and invest in cryptocurrencies, and in stock markets, all in one single place. The vision was to make a product for the global financial system that is easily accessible to everyone. The customer will first have to make investments in cryptocurrencies, then he/she can invest in share markets as per their needs. This product also has a built-in machine learning based stock prediction model which helps its users to decide which stock to invest in & when it is the right time to sell such stocks.

Figure 1.1.1

Figure 1.1.2

1.2. MOTIVATION:

The main motivation behind developing this product was to spread awareness about investing in cryptocurrency. The way cryptocurrency markets and prices react are ten times faster than the stock market. The fluctuations in cryptocurrency market prices are huge, therefore we can always store some investments in cryptocurrency which we can sell once the prices increase. Since the fluctuations in prices of cryptocurrencies are larger than that of stocks, the profit the customer would gain will be more. Then when we focus on the other functionality of the product that is investment in stock market- we have developed a hybrid machine learning algorithm that helps us in predicting the prices of stocks. The motivation behind this functionality was to ensure that the customers of this product have a profitable return to their investments. The fluctuations of the prices of the stocks are violent and

sometimes even people with immense knowledge about the stock market fail to predict the rise and dip of the prices.

Some people invest in stocks without knowing how it functions and end up losing all their money. Therefore this product uses the advantage of advancement in technology to predict stock prices thereby helping its customers to maximize profits with low risks.

Figure 1.2.1

average accuracy: 95.693

Figure 1.2.2

1.3. BACKGROUND:

A. Global Stock Market Prediction Based on Stock Chart Images Using Deep Q-Network:

In this research paper, the author has implemented Deep Q-Learning using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). This paper takes local stock market charts as input for making stock market predictions at a global level. This model helps its customers to make a profit in the global stock markets. In this project the author trained his model only on USA stock market data and then he tested it on the stock market data of different countries spanning over several years. The results showed that the input images were able to predict the stock price fluctuations across the global stock markets. The authors then tested the predicted stock market prices with the actual data of different countries, which yielded amazing results. The advantage of this model was that it could be trained on the data of relatively large market data and be tested on the data of relatively smaller markets. The results of this paper demonstrated that Artificial Intelligence (AI) based stock market price prediction models can be used in relatively smaller markets even though they don't have enough data for training.

B. Financial Trading Model with Stock Bar Chart Image Time Series with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks:

Many models have been developed using Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) & Deep Learning techniques to predict the fluctuations of stock markets. But, most of the developed models use only time series data for stock market price prediction and to identify when to buy or sell stocks. However in this paper the author uses 2-D stock market bar charts as inputs instead of using any time series data to derive the results. The author

developed his model with the help of Convolutional Neural Network with Bar Images (CNN-BI) using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). He then generated 2-D images of 30 day bar charts and trained a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) model for the proposed algorithmic stock prediction model.

The author then tested the model using different data and different market conditions. The conclusions derived was that the model was able to outperform the Buy and Hold strategy, especially in Bulls & Bears market. This was a preliminary study about one of the attempts using an unconventional approach to predict stock market prices which yielded promising results.

C. A new approach for Trading based on Long-Short Term memory technique:

In this project the author was able to develop a Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) model that included different frequencies- yearly & daily parameters that could predict the closing prices of the stock market. The algorithm used to develop this model was a combination of 2 Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) techniques. Based on the results derived from the model, we can predict the opening, closing, high and low prices thereby making it a crucial model for the investors, stakeholders, and traders. This approach proved that we can improve the stock market prediction techniques.

D. Intraday Equity Price Prediction using Deep Learning as a Measure of Market Efficiency:

In finance, market analysis suggests that past stock price and volume data aren't always effective to predict future stock market prices. In this project, the author contradicts this statement by saying that future prices can be predicted effectively. He uses two different machine learning algorithms to prove his statement. He uses flexible ML techniques to measure market efficiency. In this project he concludes that if we compare our returns over a high volume trading data then we can easily achieve our target.

E. Deep Neural Networks in High Frequency Trading:

In this paper, the author implemented a high frequency strategy using Deep Neural Network (DNN) to predict the stock market prices. The model was trained using the current time to predict the next minute price of the stock. The predictions made by the model using the high frequency strategy was used to buy and sell the stocks to yield results and further conclusions. This model has an efficiency of about 81%, which suppresses the 66% directional accuracy of the DNN.

F. HATS: A Hierarchical Graph Attention Network for Stock Movement Prediction:

Traders, investors and stakeholders have made numerous approaches to develop a model that predicts future stock prices. Researchers have started using graph structured data to develop such models. In this proposed model- HATS, the author uses a hierarchical attention network to predict stock market prices using relational data. This method collects information about different relation types and cumulates the same to the data of each company. This model has a feature extraction module. This model not only predicts the stock prices of one company but also predicts the market index movements through a graph. This model can change its performance based on the relational data used. This model has outperformed all existing models.

G. A Robust Predictive Model for Stock Price Prediction Using Deep Learning and Natural Language Processing:

There has been tons of research done on how to predict the future stock prices. Increasing the prediction efficiency is the biggest challenge. In this paper the author uses a hybrid of different Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning and Natural Learning Processing (NLP) algorithms to predict the market index movements. Based on previous available data the author predicts the future stock price using ML algorithms. Various number of classification techniques are used to predict the stock market prices and its fluctuations. Regression models have been used to predict the closing price of the stock. Then a LSTM based deep learning model was developed to predict the closing price of the stocks. Then the results of the deep learning and machine learning based model was compared. The author then collaborates the model with a sentiment analysis module on twitter data to correlate public sentiment with stock market sentiment. Based on Self Organizing Fuzzy Neural Networks, the model was trained and tested and it produced some progressive results.

H. Financial Market Directional Forecasting With Stacked Denoising Autoencoder:

Many stock market prediction algorithms have been developed but none of them have been able to attain the desirable level of efficiency. In this paper the author presents to us a deep learning model which will have a strong ability to predict the future stock market prices. A Stacked Denoising Autoencoder (SDAE) was applied to the dataset. The results were then compared with the results yielded by back propagation network and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The results showed that this model was significantly better than the other existing models.

I. Deep Learning for Stock Selection Based on High Frequency Price-Volume Data:

In the field of stock market research, the most controversial decision is to select which model we would like to train and test. Many models have been successful in getting results by using low frequency data. The main issue comes up when we have to use high frequency data. In this paper, the author illustrates how he developed a model that for predicting the stock prices using high frequency data. He constructed two different models- CNN & LSTM which

predicted the price & most profitable stock. Then he made changes to the CNN model, which enabled his model to extract high level data without losing the original information. The LSTM model on the other hand used Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to handle time series data efficiently. Then the model was tested which yielded promising results.

J. Stock Prices Prediction using Deep Learning Models:

In this paper the author uses deep learning models to predict stock market prices. He uses sparse auto encoders with 1-D residual convolutional networks to denoise the inconsistency in the available data. He then uses LSTM to predict the stock prices. Results have shown that this model has a better efficiency than one that uses Wavelet Transforms (WT) & Stacked Auto Encoders (SAEs).

K. Towards an Understanding of Cryptocurrency: A Comparative Analysis of Cryptocurrency, Foreign:

Cryptocurrency is a result of advancement in technology and a Fintech innovation. It implements the concept of digital currency, which helps the owners in various fields such as capital management, digital currency and non-monetary applications. The main aim of reading this paper was to understand cryptocurrency as a financial assets-foreign exchange and stocks. This paper focuses on the different properties of cryptocurrency such as clustering structure, volatility, risk, robustness and centrality. Cryptocurrency markets are lot more fragile than stock markets. It is very important to study the features before we invest, hold or sell digital currency.

L. An Analysis of Cryptocurrency, Bitcoin, and the Future:

In this paper we study about Bitcoin, the most famous form of cryptocurrency and its future. We study how cryptocurrencies have made a change to the global markets and investment schemes. In this paper a SWOT analysis of Bitcoin has been presented. It shows that how with technology advancement we can use digital currency as an important financial asset. This technology has been able to revolutionize digital markets globally.

II. PROJECT DESCRIPTION AND GOALS:

- The primary objective of this project was to predict the fluctuations of prices in the stock market. What many researchers do is that they develop an algorithm and stop the progress there itself. In this project my motto was to develop such a model which can be turned into a product. To have a product, it is must to have a website or app which helps it to serve its clients. In this project, I developed a website for the User Interface. The customers will be served by an easy to use website. Firstly, he/she has to create an account with his/her digital currency wallet ID. For the investments in cryptocurrency I have used Coinbase. Once the digital currency has been purchased, the user can sell, store or invest in stock market using it. So, basically the first goal was achieved by developing a fully functional website.
- The second goal or progress of this project was its primary mission that is to forecast the stock prices of a company based on the past available dataset. I developed a hybrid deep learning algorithm to forecast the prices of the future. In this project I used LSTM & seq2seq algorithms to attain my objective. After developing the code, I trained and tested the data, which yielded amazing results.
- The third goal of this project was to find out the buy-sell points of the stock. I used a reinforcement learning based agent to predict that. The recurrent actor critic model was used. In this project the user can only buy or sell one unit of stock at a given time but, once the product gets fully deployed we can invest in more than one unit thereby increasing the profits. The result shows the profits a user would incur if he/she invests a specific amount of money in a particular company.
- The final goal of this project was to help the user decide in which company he/she should invest. We compare the profitability and the volatility of the stock, that is the risk percentage and plot a graph suggesting the users in which stock he/she should invest. This helps the customers to make safe investments.

II. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION:

The website codes were written in HTML. I used CSS & Bootstrap for the design. The codes were written on Sublime Text editor. Then they were uploaded on my GitHub repository and deployed via Netlify. With the advancement of technology there was no additional requirements on the hardware or the software side. The Machine Learning codes were implemented on an online cloud based jupyter notebook environment- Google Colab. The machine learning codes were written in Python. We have used different Python Deep Learning libraries such as- tensorflow (It is the foundation library for deep learning models), numpy (array processing package), matplotlib (graph plotting library), seaborn (data visualization library) & pandas (used to import files like excel, csv, etc.). We upload the notebooks on the google drive and then import it to Colab.

2. DESIGN APPROACH AND DETAILS:

2.1. DESIGN APPROACH:

For forecasting the future prices of the stocks of a company I've developed a hybrid of the LSTM & seq2seq model. And for predicting the buy-sell points of the stock prediction I have implemented the actor critic recurrent agent. Before seq2seq model each word used to get translated into the target language with no relevance to its grammar

and phrase structure. Seq2seq changes this method of conversion by using deep learning techniques. It takes the neighbourhood of the input into consideration while translating any word. Seq2seq takes a sentence as an input and generates an output. It uses RNN to do so. Because RNN has the problem of a vanishing gradient, LSTM is used to ensure the better working of the model. It takes two inputs- one from the previous output and another from the user. The seq2seq model has the following components:

Encoder: It converts input words to the corresponding vectors using deep neural network layers. The present word and the context of it is represented by the vector. Decoder: It uses the hidden vector generated by the encoder, along with its own hidden states and the word to produce the next vector and predict the word.

Seq2Seq Model

Figure 4.1.1

LSTM is a type of a RNN. In RNN, output from the previous step is treated as an input for the next step. The problem of long-term dependencies of RNN (where it couldn't predict the word stored in the long term but could give us information from the recent memory) was solved. RNN was inefficient with gap lengths. LSTM can retain information for a long time and use it for processing and predicting the word. LSTM has a chain structure that contains four neural networks and different memory blocks called cells.

Figure 4.1.2

Information is recollected by the cells and the memory managements are done by the gates. There are three gates –

- Forget Gate: The information in the cell state that is no longer useful is removed with the forget gate. Two inputs x_t (input) and h_{t-1} (previous output) are fed to the gate and multiplied with weight matrices followed by the addition of bias. The resultant is passed through an activation function which gives an output in the form of 0's and 1's. If for a cell state the output is 0, the piece of information is forgotten and for the output 1, the information is retained for the future use.

Figure 4.1.3

- Input gate: Addition of useful information to the cell state is done by input gate. First, the information is regulated using the sigmoid function and filter the values to be remembered similar to the forget gate using inputs h_{t-1} and x_t . Then, a vector is created using tanh function that gives output from -1 to +1, which contains all the possible values from h_{t-1} and x_t . At last, the values of the vector and the regulated values are multiplied to obtain the useful information

Figure 4.1.4

- Output gate: The task of extracting useful information from the current cell state to be presented as an output is done by output gate. First, a vector is generated by applying tanh function on the cell. Then, the information is regulated using the sigmoid function and filter the values to be remembered using inputs h_{t-1} and x_t . At last, the values of the vector and the regulated values are multiplied to be sent as an output and input to the next cell.

Figure 4.1.5

An actor-critic learning agent comprises two principal components: critic module and actor module. Both modules are adaptive, consisting of variety of adjustable weights (or parameters) to be updated with TD procedures. I assumed that our agent is realized by a neural network (NN) function approximator, resulting in actor-critic neural-network (NN) reinforcement learning with a critic NN and an actor NN, as illustrated in Fig. 4.1.6.

Figure 4.1.6

Figure 4.1.7

Figure 4.1.8

The RNN-based actor-critic trading agent was implemented in Python with Tensorflow (1.15). Although their weights are updated independently, actor network and critic network use the same RNN architecture, except for the last layer, where actor has a softmax output and critic has a linear output. The specific RNN models we implemented include RNNs, long short-term memory networks (LSTM) & seq2seq. The length of a look-back period was set to 30; that is, every decision made by the agent was based on the market status of the past 30 trading days. The number of hidden layer units was set to 256.

2.2. CODES AND STANDARD: WEBSITE:

A. dashboard.html:

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
<title>Stock Market Analysis</title>
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
<link href="https://fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Nunito:300,400,700" rel="stylesheet">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="fonts/icomoon/style.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/jquery-ui.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.carousel.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.theme.default.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.theme.default.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/jquery.fancybox.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap-datepicker.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="fonts/flaticon/font/flaticon.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/aos.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style.css">
```



```
</div>
<div class="site-section" id="BTC-section">
<div class="container">
<div class="row mb-5 justify-content-center text-center" data-aos="fade-up">
<div class="col-7 text-center mb-5">
  <br><br>
<h2 class="section-title">Invest in BTC</h2>
<p class="lead">Bitcoin is ideal for speculation and investment, because of its great popularity.</p>
</div>

</div>
<div class="row align-items-stretch">
<div class="col-md-6 col-lg-12 mb-4 mb-lg-4" data-aos="fade-up">
<div class="unit-4 d-block">
<div class="unit-4-icon mb-3">
<span class="icon-wrap"><span class="text-primary icon-bitcoin"></span></span>
</div>
<div>
<h3>Did You Know?</h3>
<p>Just like a cent is the smallest unit of USD, a satoshi is the smallest unit of bitcoin, thus being the smallest denomination with which transactions can be carried out. This unit is referred to as satoshi to serve as a reference to Satoshi Nakamoto, the originator(s) of Bitcoin.</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="site-section" id="Shares-section">
<div class="container">
<div class="row mb-5 justify-content-center text-center" data-aos="fade-up">
<div class="col-7 text-center mb-5">
  <br><br>
<h2 class="section-title">Invest in Shares</h2>
<p class="lead">Shares are one of the four main investment types, along with cash, bonds and property.</p>
</div>
</div>
<div class="row align-items-stretch">
<div class="col-md-6 col-lg-12 mb-4 mb-lg-4" data-aos="fade-up">
<div class="unit-4 d-block">
<div class="unit-4-icon mb-3">
<span class="icon-wrap"><span class="text-primary icon-dollar"></span></span></span>
</div>
<div>
<h3>Did You Know?</h3>
<p>While some companies sell stock directly to investors, most only sell stock through a brokerage. Depending on the brokerage firm you choose, you may call an agent to buy stocks or simply buy and sell shares online.</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="feature-big">
<div class="container">
<div class="row mb-5 site-section">
<div class="col-lg-7" data-aos="fade-right">

```

```
</div>
<div class="col-lg-5 pl-lg-5 ml-auto mt-md-5">
<h2 class="text-black">Referrals</h2>
<p class="mb-4">Chart representing the referrals, there are two parts in this, Direct and Swastik.</p>
</div>
</div>
<div class="mt-5 row mb-5 site-section ">
<div class="col-lg-7 order-1 order-lg-2" data-aos="fade-left">

</div>

<div class="col-lg-5 pr-lg-5 mr-auto mt-5 order-2 order-lg-1">
<h2 class="text-black">Country Usage</h2>
<p class="mb-4">Here we have the usage, we have various countries for this, i.e. India, Indonesia, Pakistan, China.</p>
</div>
</div>
<div class="row mb-5 site-section">
<div class="col-lg-7" data-aos="fade-right">

</div>
<div class="col-lg-5 pl-lg-5 ml-auto mt-md-5">
<h2 class="text-black">Rating</h2>
<p class="mb-4">It clearly shows the reliability and usefulness of our product. Our customers are mostly happy with the services.</p>
</div>
</div>
<div class="mt-5 row mb-5 site-section ">
<div class="col-lg-7 order-1 order-lg-2" data-aos="fade-left">

</div>
<div class="col-lg-5 pr-lg-5 mr-auto mt-5 order-2 order-lg-1">
<h2 class="text-black">Clicks Count</h2>
<p class="mb-4">This data shows the number of clicks on the website.</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div><!-- .site-wrap -->
<script src="js/jquery-3.3.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery-ui.js"></script>
<script src="js/popper.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/owl.carousel.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.countdown.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap-datepicker.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.easing.1.3.js"></script>
<script src="js/aos.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.fancybox.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.sticky.js"></script>
<script src="js/main.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
```

B. index.html:

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
<title>Stock Market Analysis</title>
```



```
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<script type="text/javascript">
function plus(){
    document.getElementById("q").value = parseInt(document.getElementById("q").value) + 1;
    let cp = parseFloat(document.getElementById("cp").innerHTML.split(" ")[0]);
    let cbp = parseFloat(document.getElementById("cbp").innerHTML.split(" ")[0]);
    let price = cp/cbp*parseFloat(document.getElementById("q").value);
    price = price.toFixed(4);

    document.getElementById("inv").value = "Invest: "+price;
}
function minus(){
    if(document.getElementById("q").value!=0){
        document.getElementById("q").value = parseInt(document.getElementById("q").value) - 1;
        let cp = parseFloat(document.getElementById("cp").innerHTML.split(" ")[0]);
        let cbp = parseFloat(document.getElementById("cbp").innerHTML.split(" ")[0]);
        let price = cp/cbp*parseFloat(document.getElementById("q").value);
        price = price.toFixed(4);
        document.getElementById("inv").value = "Invest: "+price;
    }
}
</script>
<script src="js/jquery-3.3.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery-ui.js"></script>
<script src="js/popper.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/owl.carousel.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.countdown.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap-datepicker.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.easing.1.3.js"></script>
<script src="js/aos.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.fancybox.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.sticky.js"></script>
<script src="js/main.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
```

D. login.html:

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
<title>Stock Market Analysis</title>
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
<link href="https://fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Nunito:300,400,700" rel="stylesheet">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="fonts/icomoon/style.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/jquery-ui.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.carousel.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.theme.default.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.theme.default.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/jquery.fancybox.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap-datepicker.css">
```



```
<input type="text" id="wid" class="form-control rounded-0">
</div>
<br>
<div class="col-md-12">
<label class="text-black" for="lname">Password</label>
<input type="Password" id="pass" class="form-control rounded-0">
</div>
<br>
<div>
<input type="submit" onclick="login()" value="Login" class="btn btn-primary mr-5 mb-5" >
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<script type="text/javascript">
function login(){
let id = "32T7tzJ9WvCdwE2CgdkBeCF6B6H7zGWKRC";
let pass = "Swastik123#";
if( document.getElementById("wid").value==id && document.getElementById("pass").value==pass){
window.open("dashboard.html");
}
}
</script>
<script src="js/jquery-3.3.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery-ui.js"></script>
<script src="js/popper.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/owl.carousel.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.countdown.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap-datepicker.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.easing.1.3.js"></script>
<script src="js/aos.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.fancybox.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.sticky.js"></script>
<script src="js/main.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
```

E. predict.html:

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
<title>Stock Market Analysis</title>
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
<link href="https://fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Nunito:300,400,700" rel="stylesheet">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="fonts/icomoon/style.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/jquery-ui.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.carousel.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.theme.default.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/owl.theme.default.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/jquery.fancybox.min.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap-datepicker.css">
```



```
<div action="dashboard.html" class="p-5 bg-white justify-content-center">
<strong>Comapany Name</strong>
<br>
    AAPL
<br><br>
<strong>Currrent Price</strong>
<br>
    292.65 USD
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<br>
<br>
<br>
<br>
</div>
```

```
</div>
<script src="js/jquery-3.3.1.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery-ui.js"></script>
<script src="js/popper.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/owl.carousel.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.countdown.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap-datepicker.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.easing.1.3.js"></script>
<script src="js/aos.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.fancybox.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/jquery.sticky.js"></script>
<script src="js/main.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
```

MACHINE LEARNING ALORITHMS:

A. Predicting the price of the stock:

```
!pip install tensorflow-gpu==1.15
import sys
import warnings
if not sys.warnoptions:
    warnings.simplefilter('ignore')
import tensorflow as tf
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import pandas as pd
import pandas.util.testing as tm
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from datetime import datetime
from datetime import timedelta
from tqdm import tqdm
sns.set()
tf.compat.v1.random.set_random_seed(1234)
df = pd.read_csv('NIFTY 50.csv')
df.head()
minmax = MinMaxScaler().fit(df.iloc[:, 4:5].astype('float32'))
df_log = minmax.transform(df.iloc[:, 4:5].astype('float32'))
df_log = pd.DataFrame(df_log)
df_log.head()
```

```
simulation_size = 10
num_layers = 1
size_layer = 128
timestamp = 5
epoch = 300
dropout_rate = 0.8
test_size = 30
learning_rate = 0.01
df_train = df_log
df.shape, df_train.shape
classModel:
def __init__(
    self,
    learning_rate,
    num_layers,
    size,
    size_layer,
    output_size,
    forget_bias = 0.1,
):
def lstm_cell(size_layer):
return tf.nn.rnn_cell.LSTMCell(size_layer, state_is_tuple = False)
    rnn_cells = tf.nn.rnn_cell.MultiRNNCell(
        [lstm_cell(size_layer) for _ in range(num_layers)],
        state_is_tuple = False,
    )
    self.X = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, None, size))
    self.Y = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, output_size))
    drop = tf.contrib.rnn.DropoutWrapper(
        rnn_cells, output_keep_prob = forget_bias
    )
    self.hidden_layer = tf.placeholder(
        tf.float32, (None, num_layers * 2 * size_layer)
    )
    _, last_state = tf.nn.dynamic_rnn(
        drop, self.X, initial_state = self.hidden_layer, dtype = tf.float32
    )
with tf.variable_scope('decoder', reuse = False):
    rnn_cells_dec = tf.nn.rnn_cell.MultiRNNCell(
        [lstm_cell(size_layer) for _ in range(num_layers)], state_is_tuple = False
    )
    drop_dec = tf.contrib.rnn.DropoutWrapper(
        rnn_cells_dec, output_keep_prob = forget_bias
    )
    self.outputs, self.last_state = tf.nn.dynamic_rnn(
        drop_dec, self.X, initial_state = last_state, dtype = tf.float32
    )
    self.logits = tf.layers.dense(self.outputs[-1], output_size)
    self.cost = tf.reduce_mean(tf.square(self.Y - self.logits))
    self.optimizer = tf.train.AdamOptimizer(learning_rate).minimize(
        self.cost
    )
def calculate_accuracy(real, predict):
    real = np.array(real) + 1
    predict = np.array(predict) + 1
    percentage = 1 - np.sqrt(np.mean(np.square((real - predict) / real)))
return percentage * 100
def anchor(signal, weight):
```

```
buffer = []
last = signal[0]
for i in signal:
    smoothed_val = last * weight + (1 - weight) * i
    buffer.append(smoothed_val)
    last = smoothed_val
return buffer
defforecast():
tf.reset_default_graph()
modelInn=Model(
learning_rate,num_layers,df_log.shape[1],size_layer,df_log.shape[1],dropout_rate
)
sess=tf.InteractiveSession()
sess.run(tf.global_variables_initializer())
date_ori=pd.to_datetime(df.iloc[:,0]).tolist()
pbar=tqdm(range(epoch),desc='train loop')
foriinpbar:
init_value=np.zeros((1,num_layers*2*size_layer))
total_loss,total_acc=[],[]
forkinrange(0,df_train.shape[0]-1,timestamp):
index=min(k+timestamp,df_train.shape[0]-1)
batch_x=np.expand_dims(
df_train.iloc[k:index,:].values,axis=0
)
batch_y=df_train.iloc[k+1:index+1,:].values
logits,last_state,_loss=sess.run(
[modelInn.logits,modelInn.last_state,modelInn.optimizer,modelInn.cost],
feed_dict={
modelInn.X:batch_x,
modelInn.Y:batch_y,
modelInn.hidden_layer:init_value,
},
)
init_value=last_state
total_loss.append(loss)
total_acc.append(calculate_accuracy(batch_y[:,0],logits[:,0]))
pbar.set_postfix(cost=np.mean(total_loss),acc=np.mean(total_acc))
future_day=test_size
output_predict=np.zeros((df_train.shape[0]+future_day,df_train.shape[1]))
output_predict[0]=df_train.iloc[0]
upper_b=(df_train.shape[0]//timestamp)*timestamp
init_value=np.zeros((1,num_layers*2*size_layer))
forkinrange(0,(df_train.shape[0]//timestamp)*timestamp,timestamp):
out_logits,last_state=sess.run(
[modelInn.logits,modelInn.last_state],
feed_dict={
modelInn.X:np.expand_dims(
df_train.iloc[k:k+timestamp],axis=0
),
modelInn.hidden_layer:init_value,
},
)
init_value=last_state
output_predict[k+1:k+timestamp+1]=out_logits
ifupper_b!=df_train.shape[0]:
out_logits,last_state=sess.run(
[modelInn.logits,modelInn.last_state],
feed_dict={
```

```
modelnn.X:np.expand_dims(df_train.iloc[upper_b:],axis=0),
modelnn.hidden_layer:init_value,
},
)
output_predict[upper_b+1:df_train.shape[0]+1]=out_logits
future_day-=1
date_ori.append(date_ori[-1]+timedelta(days=1))
init_value=last_state
foriinrange(future_day):
o=output_predict[-future_day-timestamp+i:-future_day+i]
out_logits,last_state=sess.run(
[modelnn.logits,modelnn.last_state],
feed_dict={
modelnn.X:np.expand_dims(o,axis=0),
modelnn.hidden_layer:init_value,
},
)

init_value=last_state
output_predict[-future_day+i]=out_logits[-1]
date_ori.append(date_ori[-1]+timedelta(days=1))
output_predict=minmax.inverse_transform(output_predict)
deep_future=anchor(output_predict[:,0],0.3)
returndeep_future[-test_size:]
results=[]
foriinrange(simulation_size):
print('simulation %d'%(i+1))
results.append(forecast())
date_ori = pd.to_datetime(df.iloc[:, 0]).tolist()
for i in range(test_size):
date_ori.append(date_ori[-1] + timedelta(days = 1))
date_ori = pd.Series(date_ori).dt.strftime(date_format = '%Y-%m-%d').tolist()
date_ori[-5:]
accepted_results = []
for r in results:
if (np.array(r[-test_size:]) < np.min(df['Close'])).sum() == 0 and \
(np.array(r[-test_size:]) > np.max(df['Close']) * 2).sum() == 0:
accepted_results.append(r)
len(accepted_results)
accuracies = [calculate_accuracy(df['Close'].values, r[:-test_size]) for r in accepted_results]
plt.figure(figsize = (15, 5))
for no, r in enumerate(accepted_results):
plt.plot(r, label = 'forecast %d'%(no + 1))
plt.plot(df['Close'], label = 'true trend', c = 'black')
plt.legend()
plt.title('average accuracy: %.4f'%(np.mean(accuracies)))
x_range_future = np.arange(len(results[0]))
plt.xticks(x_range_future[::30], date_ori[::30])
plt.show()
```

B. Predicting when to buy and sell shares:

```
!pip install tensorflow-gpu==1.15
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import tensorflow as tf
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
```

```
import pandas.util.testing as tm
sns.set()
df = pd.read_csv('GOOG.csv')
df.head()
from collections import deque
import random

class Actor:
    def __init__(self, name, input_size, output_size, size_layer):
        with tf.variable_scope(name):
            self.X = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, None, input_size))
            self.hidden_layer = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, 2 * size_layer))
            cell = tf.nn.rnn_cell.LSTMCell(size_layer, state_is_tuple = False)
            self.rnn, self.last_state = tf.nn.dynamic_rnn(inputs=self.X, cell=cell,
                dtype=tf.float32,
                initial_state=self.hidden_layer)
            self.logits = tf.layers.dense(self.rnn[:, -1], output_size)

class Critic:
    def __init__(self, name, input_size, output_size, size_layer, learning_rate):
        with tf.variable_scope(name):
            self.X = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, None, input_size))
            self.Y = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, output_size))
            self.hidden_layer = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, 2 * size_layer))
            self.REWARD = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, 1))
            feed_critic = tf.layers.dense(self.X, size_layer, activation = tf.nn.relu)
            cell = tf.nn.rnn_cell.LSTMCell(size_layer, state_is_tuple = False)
            self.rnn, self.last_state = tf.nn.dynamic_rnn(inputs=self.X, cell=cell,
                dtype=tf.float32,
                initial_state=self.hidden_layer)
            feed_critic = tf.layers.dense(self.rnn[:, -1], output_size, activation = tf.nn.relu) + self.Y
            feed_critic = tf.layers.dense(feed_critic, size_layer // 2, activation = tf.nn.relu)
            self.logits = tf.layers.dense(feed_critic, 1)
            self.cost = tf.reduce_mean(tf.square(self.REWARD - self.logits))
            self.optimizer = tf.train.AdamOptimizer(learning_rate).minimize(self.cost)

class Agent:
    LEARNING_RATE = 0.001
    BATCH_SIZE = 32
    LAYER_SIZE = 256
    OUTPUT_SIZE = 3
    EPSILON = 0.5
    DECAY_RATE = 0.005
    MIN_EPSILON = 0.1
    GAMMA = 0.99
    MEMORIES = deque()
    MEMORY_SIZE = 300
    COPY = 1000
    T_COPY = 0

    def __init__(self, state_size, window_size, trend, skip):
        self.state_size = state_size
        self.window_size = window_size
        self.half_window = window_size // 2
        self.trend = trend
        self.INITIAL_FEATURES = np.zeros((4, self.state_size))
```

```
self.skip = skip
tf.reset_default_graph()
self.actor = Actor('actor-original', self.state_size, self.OUTPUT_SIZE, self.LAYER_SIZE)
self.actor_target = Actor('actor-target', self.state_size, self.OUTPUT_SIZE, self.LAYER_SIZE)
self.critic = Critic('critic-original', self.state_size, self.OUTPUT_SIZE, self.LAYER_SIZE, self.LEARNING_RATE)
self.critic_target = Critic('critic-target', self.state_size, self.OUTPUT_SIZE,
                           self.LAYER_SIZE, self.LEARNING_RATE)
self.grad_critic = tf.gradients(self.critic.logits, self.critic.Y)
self.actor_critic_grad = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, [None, self.OUTPUT_SIZE])
weights_actor = tf.get_collection(tf.GraphKeys.TRAINABLE_VARIABLES, scope='actor')
self.grad_actor = tf.gradients(self.actor.logits, weights_actor, -self.actor_critic_grad)
grads = zip(self.grad_actor, weights_actor)
self.optimizer = tf.train.AdamOptimizer(self.LEARNING_RATE).apply_gradients(grads)
self.sess = tf.InteractiveSession()
self.sess.run(tf.global_variables_initializer())

def _assign(self, from_name, to_name):
    from_w = tf.get_collection(tf.GraphKeys.TRAINABLE_VARIABLES, scope=from_name)
    to_w = tf.get_collection(tf.GraphKeys.TRAINABLE_VARIABLES, scope=to_name)
    for i in range(len(from_w)):

        assign_op = to_w[i].assign(from_w[i])
        self.sess.run(assign_op)
def _memorize(self, state, action, reward, new_state, dead, rnn_state):
    self.MEMORIES.append((state, action, reward, new_state, dead, rnn_state))
    if len(self.MEMORIES) > self.MEMORY_SIZE:
        self.MEMORIES.popleft()
def _select_action(self, state):
    if np.random.rand() < self.EPSILON:
        action = np.random.randint(self.OUTPUT_SIZE)
    else:
        prediction = self.sess.run(self.actor.logits, feed_dict={self.actor.X:[state]})[0]
        action = np.argmax(prediction)
    return action
def _construct_memories_and_train(self, replay):
    states = np.array([a[0] for a in replay])
    new_states = np.array([a[3] for a in replay])
    init_values = np.array([a[-1] for a in replay])
    Q = self.sess.run(self.actor.logits, feed_dict={self.actor.X: states,
                                                  self.actor.hidden_layer: init_values})
    Q_target = self.sess.run(self.actor_target.logits, feed_dict={self.actor_target.X: states,
                                                                self.actor_target.hidden_layer: init_values})
    grads = self.sess.run(self.grad_critic, feed_dict={self.critic.X:states, self.critic.Y:Q,
                                                       self.critic.hidden_layer: init_values})[0]
    self.sess.run(self.optimizer, feed_dict={self.actor.X:states, self.actor_critic_grad:grads,
                                             self.actor.hidden_layer: init_values})
    rewards = np.array([a[2] for a in replay]).reshape((-1, 1))
    rewards_target = self.sess.run(self.critic_target.logits,
                                   feed_dict={self.critic_target.X:new_states,self.critic_target.Y:Q_target,
                                             self.critic_target.hidden_layer: init_values})
    for i in range(len(replay)):
        if not replay[0][-2]:
            rewards[i] += self.GAMMA * rewards_target[i]
    cost, _ = self.sess.run([self.critic.cost, self.critic.optimizer],
                           feed_dict={self.critic.X:states, self.critic.Y:Q, self.critic.REWARD:rewards,
                                       self.critic.hidden_layer: init_values})
    return cost
def get_state(self, t):
```

```
window_size = self.window_size + 1
d = t - window_size + 1
block = self.trend[d : t + 1] if d >= 0 else -d * [self.trend[0]] + self.trend[0 : t + 1]
res = []
for i in range(window_size - 1):
    res.append(block[i + 1] - block[i])
return np.array(res)
def buy(self, initial_money):
starting_money = initial_money
states_sell = []
states_buy = []
inventory = []
state = self.get_state(0)
init_value = np.zeros((1, 2 * self.LAYER_SIZE))
for k in range(self.INITIAL_FEATURES.shape[0]):
    self.INITIAL_FEATURES[k,:] = state
for t in range(0, len(self.trend) - 1, self.skip):

if np.random.rand() < self.EPSILON:
    action = np.random.randint(self.OUTPUT_SIZE)
else:
    action, last_state = self.sess.run([self.actor.logits,
                                        self.actor.last_state],
                                        feed_dict={self.actor.X:[self.INITIAL_FEATURES],
                                                    self.actor.hidden_layer:init_value})
    action, init_value = np.argmax(action[0]), last_state
    next_state = self.get_state(t + 1)
    if action == 1 and initial_money >= self.trend[t]:
inventory.append(self.trend[t])
initial_money -= self.trend[t]
states_buy.append(t)
print('day %d: buy 1 unit at price %f, total balance %f' % (t, self.trend[t], initial_money))
    elif action == 2 and len(inventory):
bought_price = inventory.pop(0)
initial_money += self.trend[t]
states_sell.append(t)
    try:
invest = ((close[t] - bought_price) / bought_price) * 100
    except:
invest = 0
    print(
'day %d, sell 1 unit at price %f, investment %f %%, total balance %f,'
% (t, close[t], invest, initial_money)
)
    new_state = np.append([self.get_state(t + 1)], self.INITIAL_FEATURES[:3, :], axis = 0)
self.INITIAL_FEATURES = new_state
invest = ((initial_money - starting_money) / starting_money) * 100
total_gains = initial_money - starting_money
return states_buy, states_sell, total_gains, invest
def train(self, iterations, checkpoint, initial_money):
for i in range(iterations):
total_profit = 0
inventory = []
state = self.get_state(0)
starting_money = initial_money
init_value = np.zeros((1, 2 * self.LAYER_SIZE))
for k in range(self.INITIAL_FEATURES.shape[0]):
self.INITIAL_FEATURES[k,:] = state
```

```

for t in range(0, len(self.trend) - 1, self.skip):
    if (self.T_COPY + 1) % self.COPY == 0:
        self._assign('actor-original', 'actor-target')
        self._assign('critic-original', 'critic-target')
        if np.random.rand() < self.EPSILON:
            action = np.random.randint(self.OUTPUT_SIZE)
        else:
            action, last_state = self.sess.run([self.actor.logits,
                                                self.actor.last_state],
                                                feed_dict={self.actor.X:[self.INITIAL_FEATURES],
                                                            self.actor.hidden_layer:init_value})
            action, init_value = np.argmax(action[0]), last_state
            next_state = self.get_state(t + 1)
            if action == 1 and starting_money >= self.trend[t]:
                inventory.append(self.trend[t])
                starting_money -= self.trend[t]
            elif action == 2 and len(inventory) > 0:
                bought_price = inventory.pop(0)
                total_profit += self.trend[t] - bought_price
                starting_money += self.trend[t]
                invest = ((starting_money - initial_money) / initial_money)
            new_state = np.append([self.get_state(t + 1)], self.INITIAL_FEATURES[:3, :], axis = 0)
            self._memorize(self.INITIAL_FEATURES, action, invest, new_state,
                           starting_money < initial_money, init_value[0])
            batch_size = min(len(self.MEMORIES), self.BATCH_SIZE)
            self.INITIAL_FEATURES = new_state
            replay = random.sample(self.MEMORIES, batch_size)
            cost = self._construct_memories_and_train(replay)
            self.T_COPY += 1
            self.EPSILON = self.MIN_EPSILON + (1.0 - self.MIN_EPSILON) * np.exp(-self.DECAY_RATE * i)
        if (i+1) % checkpoint == 0:
            print('epoch: %d, total rewards: %f.3, cost: %f, total money: %f'%(i + 1, total_profit, cost,
                                                                              starting_money))

```

```

close = df.Close.values.tolist()
initial_money = 10000
window_size = 30
skip = 1
batch_size = 32
agent = Agent(state_size = window_size,
              window_size = window_size,
              trend = close,
              skip = skip)
agent.train(iterations = 100, checkpoint = 5, initial_money = initial_money)
states_buy, states_sell, total_gains, invest = agent.buy(initial_money = initial_money)
fig = plt.figure(figsize = (15,5))
plt.plot(close, color='r', lw=2.)
plt.plot(close, '^', markersize=10, color='m', label = 'buying signal', markevery = states_buy)
plt.plot(close, 'v', markersize=10, color='k', label = 'selling signal', markevery = states_sell)
plt.title('total gains %f, total investment %f%%'%(total_gains, invest))
plt.legend()
plt.show()

```

C. Predicting which stock to buy

```

import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import pandas.util.testing as tm
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
sns.set()

```

```

directory = ""
ori_name = ['ACN.csv', 'AMZN.csv', 'CTSH.csv', 'FB.csv', 'GOOG.csv',
            'IBM.csv', 'INFY.csv', 'MSFT.csv', 'TCS.NS.csv', 'WIT.csv']
stocks = [directory + s for s in ori_name]
stocks
dfs = [pd.read_csv(s)[['Date', 'Close']] for s in stocks]
from functools import reduce
data = reduce(lambda left, right: pd.merge(left, right, on='Date'), dfs).iloc[:, 1:]
data.head()
returns = data.pct_change()
mean_daily_returns = returns.mean()
volatilities = returns.std()
mean_daily_returns * 252
volatilities * 252
combine = pd.DataFrame({'returns': mean_daily_returns * 252,
                       'volatility': volatilities * 252})
g = sns.jointplot("volatility", "returns", data=combine, kind="reg", height=7)
for i in range(combine.shape[0]):
    plt.annotate(ori_name[i].replace('.csv', ''), (combine.iloc[i, 1], combine.iloc[i, 0]))
plt.text(0, -1.5, 'SELL', fontsize=25)
plt.text(0, 1.0, 'BUY', fontsize=25)
plt.show()

```

2.3. Constraints, Alternatives and Tradeoffs

- The main drawback of using seq2seq is that the output relies a little too much on the hidden state of the final encoder. Thereby making it difficult to deal with larger datasets.
- The main issues of using LSTM was that it takes a lot of time to get trained, uses a lot of memory & that LSTM is very much sensitive to different weight initializations.
- The actor critic recurrent model isn't good in nonbootstrapping methods. When we use function approximator, the agent is unstable and the agent needs exploration conditions.

III.SCHEDULE, TASKS AND MILESTONES

Table 5.1: Schedule

Tentative Dates	Plan of Action
December	Deciding the topic & figuring out the progress structure
January	Literature Review & deciding the algorithms to focus on
February	Working on the website & algorithm to predict stock prices
March	Working on the agent which decides when to buy or sell shares
April	Working on the code where we decide which company we should invest in
May	Report, video and poster

Table 5.2: Tasks

Task ID	Task Name	Description	Status
1	Background Research- Existing Models, Literature Review	During the background research, I went through all the existing methods to predict the stock market prices. I learnt about the different models from various research papers.	Completed
2	Proposed Algorithm	After going through the different existing algorithms, I measured the pros and cons of all of them and finally decided on the techniques I'll be using for the implementation.	Completed
3	Review 1	Explained about the area of research, motive and objective behind selecting that topic and proposed algorithm.	Completed
4	Incorporating changes	Made changes to the literature survey and incorporated few more objectives.	Completed
5	60% Implementation	The website and initial algorithm for predicting	Completed

		stock market prices was developed.	
6	Review 2	Showed by implementation and spoke about the future scope.	Completed
7	Incorporating changes	Made changes as desired by the panel of faculties.	Completed
8	100% Implementation	All the codes and algorithms were completed, thereby making my model ready.	Completed
9	Incorporating changes	Made all changes suggested by faculty.	Completed
10	Documentation & Review 3	Made the report, PPT, video and poster for the upcoming review.	Completed

Table 5.3: Milstones

Milestone	Date of Completion
Literature Review	06-01-2020
Proposed Algorithm	20-01-2020
Website	14-02-2020
Code to forecast stock price	28-02-2020
Code to find buy-sell points	16-03-2020
Code to find which company to invest in	31-03-2020
Project Completion	23-05-2020

3. PROJECT DEMONSTRATION

WEBSITE: <https://swastikcapstone.netlify.app/>

Wallet ID: 32T7tzJ9WvCdwE2CgdkBeCF6B6H7zGWKRC

Password: Swastik123#

STOCK PREDICTION:

A. Predicting the price of the stock:


```
[1] ERROR: tensorflow-probability 0.10.0rc0 has requirement gast>=0.3.2, but you'll have gast 0.2.2 which is incompatible.
Installing collected packages: tensorflow-estimator, tensorboard, gast, tensorflow-gpu
Found existing installation: tensorflow-estimator 2.2.0
Uninstalling tensorflow-estimator-2.2.0:
Successfully uninstalled tensorflow-estimator-2.2.0
Found existing installation: tensorboard 2.2.1
Uninstalling tensorboard-2.2.1:
Successfully uninstalled tensorboard-2.2.1
Found existing installation: gast 0.3.3
Uninstalling gast-0.3.3:
Successfully uninstalled gast-0.3.3
Successfully installed gast-0.2.2 tensorboard-1.15.0 tensorflow-estimator-1.15.1 tensorflow-gpu-1.15.0

[2] import sys
import warnings

if not sys.warnoptions:
    warnings.simplefilter('ignore')

import tensorflow as tf
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import pandas as pd
import pandas.util.testing as tm
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from datetime import datetime
from datetime import timedelta
from tqdm import tqdm
sns.set()
tf.compat.v1.random.set_random_seed(1234)
```



```
[4] df = pd.read_csv('NIFTY 50.csv')
df.head()

   Date      Open      High      Low      Close  Shares Traded  Turnover (Rs. Cr)
0 01-Jan-20 12202.15 12222.20 12165.30 12182.50      304078039      10445.68
1 02-Jan-20 12198.55 12289.90 12195.25 12282.20      407697594      15256.55
2 03-Jan-20 12261.10 12265.60 12191.35 12226.65      428770054      16827.27
3 06-Jan-20 12170.60 12179.10 11974.20 11993.05      396501419      16869.22
4 07-Jan-20 12079.10 12152.15 12005.35 12052.95      447818617      17797.68

[5] minmax = MinMaxScaler().fit(df.iloc[:, 4:5].astype('float32'))
df_log = minmax.transform(df.iloc[:, 4:5].astype('float32'))
df_log = pd.DataFrame(df_log)
df_log.head()

   0  0.962164
1  0.983144
2  0.971455
3  0.922297
4  0.934902

simulation_size = 10
num_layers = 1
size_layer = 128
```



```
[6] simulation_size = 10
num_layers = 1
size_layer = 128
timestamp = 5
epoch = 300
dropout_rate = 0.8
test_size = 30
learning_rate = 0.01

df_train = df_log
df.shape, df_train.shape

((82, 7), (82, 1))

class Model:
    def __init__(self, learning_rate, num_layers, size, size_layer, output_size, forget_bias = 0.1,):
        self.learning_rate = learning_rate
        self.num_layers = num_layers
        self.size = size
        self.size_layer = size_layer
        self.output_size = output_size
        self.forget_bias = forget_bias

    def lstm_cell(size_layer):
        return tf.nn.rnn_cell.LSTMCell(size_layer, state_is_tuple = False)

    rnn_cells = tf.nn.rnn_cell.MultiRNNCell([lstm_cell(size_layer) for _ in range(num_layers)], state_is_tuple = False, )
    self.x = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, None, size))
    self.y = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, output_size))
```



```
state_is_tuple = False,
)
self.x = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, None, size))
self.y = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, (None, output_size))
drop = tf.contrib.rnn.DropoutWrapper(
    rnn_cells, output_keep_prob = forget_bias
)
self.hidden_layer = tf.placeholder(
    tf.float32, (None, num_layers * 2 * size_layer)
)
self.outputs, self.last_state = tf.nn.dynamic_rnn(
    drop, self.x, initial_state = self.hidden_layer, dtype = tf.float32
)
self.logits = tf.layers.dense(self.outputs[-1], output_size)
self.cost = tf.reduce_mean(tf.square(self.y - self.logits))
self.optimizer = tf.train.AdamOptimizer(learning_rate).minimize(
    self.cost
)

def calculate_accuracy(real, predict):
    real = np.array(real) + 1
    predict = np.array(predict) + 1
    percentage = 1 - np.sqrt(np.mean(np.square((real - predict) / real)))
    return percentage * 100

def anchor(signal, weight):
    buffer = []
    last = signal[0]
    for i in signal:
        smoothed_val = last * weight + (1 - weight) * i
        buffer.append(smoothed_val)
        last = smoothed_val
    return buffer
```



```
def forecast():
    tf.reset_default_graph()
    modelnn = Model(
        learning_rate, num_layers, df_log.shape[1], size_layer, df_log.shape[1], dropout_rate
    )
    sess = tf.InteractiveSession()
    sess.run(tf.global_variables_initializer())
    date_ori = pd.to_datetime(df.iloc[:, 0]).tolist()

    pbar = tqdm(range(epoch), desc = 'train loop')
    for i in pbar:
        init_value = np.zeros((1, num_layers * 2 * size_layer))
        total_loss, total_acc = [], []
        for k in range(0, df_train.shape[0] - 1, timestamp):
            index = min(k + timestamp, df_train.shape[0] - 1)
            batch_x = np.expand_dims(
                df_train.iloc[k : index, :].values, axis = 0
            )
            batch_y = df_train.iloc[k + 1 : index + 1, :].values
            logits, last_state, loss = sess.run(
                [modelnn.logits, modelnn.last_state, modelnn.optimizer, modelnn.cost],
                feed_dict = {
                    modelnn.x: batch_x,
                    modelnn.y: batch_y,
                    modelnn.hidden_layer: init_value,
                },
            )
            init_value = last_state
            total_loss.append(loss)
            total_acc.append(calculate_accuracy(batch_y[:, 0], logits[:, 0]))
        pbar.set_postfix(cost = np.mean(total_loss), acc = np.mean(total_acc))
```

```
future_day = test_size

output_predict = np.zeros((df_train.shape[0] + future_day, df_train.shape[1]))
output_predict[0] = df_train.iloc[0]
upper_b = (df_train.shape[0] // timestamp) * timestamp
init_value = np.zeros(1, num_layers * 2 * size_layer)

for k in range(0, (df_train.shape[0] // timestamp) * timestamp, timestamp):
    out_logits, last_state = sess.run(
        [modelnn.logits, modelnn.last_state],
        feed_dict = {
            modelnn.X: np.expand_dims(
                df_train.iloc[k : k + timestamp], axis = 0
            ),
            modelnn.hidden_layer: init_value,
        },
    )
    init_value = last_state
    output_predict[k + 1 : k + timestamp + 1] = out_logits

if upper_b != df_train.shape[0]:
    out_logits, last_state = sess.run(
        [modelnn.logits, modelnn.last_state],
        feed_dict = {
            modelnn.X: np.expand_dims(df_train.iloc[upper_b:], axis = 0),
            modelnn.hidden_layer: init_value,
        },
    )
    output_predict[upper_b + 1 : df_train.shape[0] + 1] = out_logits
    future_day -= 1
    date_ori.append(date_ori[-1] + timedelta(days = 1))

init_value = last_state
```

```
date_ori.append(date_ori[-1] + timedelta(days = 1))

init_value = last_state

for i in range(future_day):
    o = output_predict[-future_day - timestamp + i : -future_day + 1]
    out_logits, last_state = sess.run(
        [modelnn.logits, modelnn.last_state],
        feed_dict = {
            modelnn.X: np.expand_dims(o, axis = 0),
            modelnn.hidden_layer: init_value,
        },
    )
    init_value = last_state
    output_predict[-future_day + i] = out_logits[-1]
    date_ori.append(date_ori[-1] + timedelta(days = 1))

output_predict = minmax.inverse_transform(output_predict)
deep_future = anchor(output_predict[:, 0], 0.4)

return deep_future

results = []
for i in range(simulation_size):
    print("simulation %d" % (i + 1))
    results.append(forecast())

...
simulation 1
WARNING:tensorflow:From <ipython-input-7-d01d21f09afe>:12: LSTMCell._init__ (from tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl) is deprecated and will be
Instructions for updating:
This class is equivalent as tf.keras.layers.LSTMCell, and will be replaced by that in Tensorflow 2.0.
WARNING:tensorflow:<tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f68b080d518>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon be
WARNING:tensorflow:From <ipython-input-7-d01d21f09afe>:16: MultiInputCell._init__ (from tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl) is deprecated and will
Instructions for updating:
This class is equivalent as tf.keras.layers.MultiInputCell, and will be replaced by that in Tensorflow 2.0.
```

```
WARNING:tensorflow:From <tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f683f485a20>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon
/usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/client/session.py:1750: UserWarning: An interactive session is already active. Thi
warnings.warn("An interactive session is already active. This can '
train loop: 100% [██████████] 300/300 [00:25:00:00, 11.991t/s, acc=94.8, cost=0.00758]
simulation 4
WARNING:tensorflow:From <tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f68388a14e0>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon
/usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/client/session.py:1750: UserWarning: An interactive session is already active. Thi
warnings.warn("An interactive session is already active. This can '
train loop: 100% [██████████] 300/300 [00:23:00:00, 12.781t/s, acc=96.1, cost=0.00477]
simulation 5
WARNING:tensorflow:From <tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f6837eab9e8>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon
/usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/client/session.py:1750: UserWarning: An interactive session is already active. Thi
warnings.warn("An interactive session is already active. This can '
train loop: 100% [██████████] 300/300 [00:24:00:00, 12.321t/s, acc=93.9, cost=0.0101]
simulation 6
WARNING:tensorflow:From <tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f6836cf3a20>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon
/usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/client/session.py:1750: UserWarning: An interactive session is already active. Thi
warnings.warn("An interactive session is already active. This can '
train loop: 100% [██████████] 300/300 [00:23:00:00, 12.661t/s, acc=94.6, cost=0.00785]
simulation 7
WARNING:tensorflow:From <tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f6835abf9e8>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon
/usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/client/session.py:1750: UserWarning: An interactive session is already active. Thi
warnings.warn("An interactive session is already active. This can '
train loop: 100% [██████████] 300/300 [00:24:00:00, 12.481t/s, acc=94.3, cost=0.00851]
simulation 8
WARNING:tensorflow:From <tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f6834908ef0>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon
/usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/client/session.py:1750: UserWarning: An interactive session is already active. Thi
warnings.warn("An interactive session is already active. This can '
train loop: 100% [██████████] 300/300 [00:24:00:00, 12.011t/s, acc=92.1, cost=0.0185]
simulation 9
WARNING:tensorflow:From <tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f6833751e48>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon
/usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/client/session.py:1750: UserWarning: An interactive session is already active. Thi
warnings.warn("An interactive session is already active. This can '
train loop: 100% [██████████] 300/300 [00:24:00:00, 12.031t/s, acc=94.2, cost=0.00867]
simulation 10
WARNING:tensorflow:From <tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f683259c9e8>; Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon
/usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/client/session.py:1750: UserWarning: An interactive session is already active. Thi
warnings.warn("An interactive session is already active. This can '
train loop: 100% [██████████] 300/300 [00:24:00:00, 12.031t/s, acc=94.2, cost=0.00867]
```

```
colab.research.google.com/drive/1koUvwiWCbdeolK4GyKAhWhxThCqTkvM#scrollTo=YHn3i1MMWbVcM
```

```
Review3.ipynb
```

```
File Edit View Insert Runtime Tools Help All changes saved
```

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RAM 100% Disk
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```
Editing
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```
Files
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```
Upload Refresh Mount Drive
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```
sample_data
```

```
NIFTY 50.csv
```

```
[10] date_ori = pd.to_datetime(df.iloc[:, 0]).tolist()
for i in range(test_size):
    date_ori.append(date_ori[-1] + timedelta(days = 1))
date_ori = pd.Series(date_ori).dt.strftime(date_format = '%Y-%m-%d').tolist()
date_ori[-5:]
['2020-05-26', '2020-05-27', '2020-05-28', '2020-05-29', '2020-05-30']
```

```
[11] accepted_results = []
for r in results:
    if (np.array(r[-test_size:]) < np.min(df['close'])).sum() == 0 and \
        (np.array(r[-test_size:]) > np.max(df['close']) * 2).sum() == 0:
        accepted_results.append(r)
len(accepted_results)
```

```
accuracies = [calculate_accuracy(df['close'].values, r[:-test_size]) for r in accepted_results]
```

```
plt.figure(figsize = (15, 5))
for no, r in enumerate(accepted_results):
    plt.plot(r, label = 'forecast %d'%(no + 1))
plt.plot(df['close'], label = 'true trend', c = 'black')
plt.legend()
plt.title('average accuracy: %.4f'%(np.mean(accuracies)))
```

```
x_range_future = np.arange(len(results[0]))
plt.xticks(x_range_future[:30], date_ori[:30])
plt.show()
```

Disk 75.05 GB available

B. Predicting when to buy and sell shares:

```
Review3.ipynb - Colaboratory
```

```
colab.research.google.com/drive/1HNLIUy8eZaFIDYwG5VEQnqFn6LUBHQw
```

```
Review3.ipynb
```

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RAM 100% Disk
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Editing
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Files
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Upload Refresh Mount Drive
```

```
sample_data
```

```
GOOG.csv
```

```
!pip install tensorflow-gpu==1.15
```

```
Collecting tensorflow-gpu==1.15
  Downloading https://files.pythonhosted.org/packages/a5/ad/933140e74973fb917a194ab814785e7c2368ac5deed663a509fe9579b6/tensorflow_gpu-1.15.0-cp36-cp36m-linux_x86_64.whl (411.5MB)
Requirement already satisfied: keras-applications>=1.0.8 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (1.0.8)
Requirement already satisfied: absl-py>=0.7.0 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (0.9.0)
Requirement already satisfied: google-pasta>=0.1.6 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (0.2.0)
Requirement already satisfied: keras-preprocessing>=1.0.5 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (1.1.0)
Requirement already satisfied: grpcio>=1.6.0 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (1.28.1)
Requirement already satisfied: protobuf>=3.6.1 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (3.10.0)
Requirement already satisfied: wheel>=0.26 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (0.34.2)
Requirement already satisfied: six>=1.10.0 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (1.12.0)
Requirement already satisfied: termcolor>=1.1.0 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (1.1.0)
Collecting tensorboard<1.16.0, >=1.15.0
  Downloading https://files.pythonhosted.org/packages/1e/e9/d34747a97f7f18f48a5ed4a86907f3b345cd09f0a085068ba867db246/tensorboard-1.15.0-py3-none-any.whl (3.8MB)
Requirement already satisfied: astor>=0.6.0 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (0.8.1)
Requirement already satisfied: opt-einsum>=2.3.2 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (3.2.1)
Requirement already satisfied: wrapt>=1.11.1 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (1.12.1)
Collecting tensorflow-estimator==1.15.1
  Downloading https://files.pythonhosted.org/packages/d6/62/2ee9cd74c9fa2fa50877847ba560b260f5d6fb70ee0595203082dafcc0d/tensorflow_estimator-1.15.1-py3-none-any.whl (512KB)
Requirement already satisfied: numpy<2.0, >=1.16.0 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (1.18.4)
Collecting gast==0.2.2
  Downloading https://files.pythonhosted.org/packages/4e/35/11749bf99b2d4e3cebd455ca22590bd7c2c62b9d38ac4847f4687421/gast-0.2.2.tar.gz
Requirement already satisfied: h5py in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from keras-applications>=1.0.8->tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (2.10.0)
Requirement already satisfied: setuptools in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from protobuf>=3.6.1->tensorflow-gpu==1.15) (46.3.0)
Requirement already satisfied: markdown>=2.6.8 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-estimator==1.15) (3.1.1)
Requirement already satisfied: werkzeug>=0.11.15 in /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages (from tensorflow-estimator==1.15) (1.1.0)
Building wheels for collected packages: gast
  Building wheel for gast (setup.py) ... done
  Created wheel for gast: filename=gast-0.2.2-cp36-none-any.whl size=7540 sha256=2729ae6074499922fcc41c147c71fae5741f365ffc35a759a4412d19158dc
  Stored in directory: /root/.cache/pip/wheels/5c/2e/7e/a1d44dfceebec381f378ce7743ac3ced3699feb89bcbfdadadd
Successfully built gast
ERROR: tensorflow 2.2.0 has requirement gast>=0.3.3, but you'll have gast 0.2.2 which is incompatible.
```

Disk 76.72 GB available

The image displays three sequential screenshots of a Google Colab notebook titled 'Review3.ipynb'. The first screenshot shows an error message: 'ERROR: tensorflow-probability 0.10.0rc0 has requirement gast>=0.3.2, but you'll have gast 0.2.2 which is incompatible.' It lists the installation and uninstallation of tensorflow-board, tensorflow-estimator, and gast. Below the error, a code cell contains imports for numpy, pandas, tensorflow, matplotlib, seaborn, and testing, followed by a call to read a CSV file named 'GOOG.csv' and a display of its head. The second screenshot shows the same code cell after execution, displaying a table of stock data for Google (GOOG) from May 16, 2019, to May 22, 2019. The table includes columns for Date, Open, High, Low, Close, Adj Close, and Volume. The third screenshot shows the code cell with Python classes for Actor, Critic, and Agent. The Actor class uses an LSTM cell, the Critic class uses a dense layer, and the Agent class manages the training process with various hyperparameters like learning rate, batch size, and epsilon.


```
[ ]
self.critic_target = Critic("critic-target", self.state_size, self.OUTPUT_SIZE,
                             self.LAYER_SIZE, self.LEARNING_RATE)
self.grad_critic = tf.gradients(self.critic.logits, self.critic.Y)
self.actor_critic_grad = tf.placeholder(tf.float32, [None, self.OUTPUT_SIZE])
weights_actor = tf.get_collection(tf.GraphKeys.TRAINABLE_VARIABLES, scope='actor')
self.grad_actor = tf.gradients(self.actor.logits, weights_actor, -self.actor_critic_grad)
grads = zip(self.grad_actor, weights_actor)
self.optimizer = tf.train.AdamOptimizer(self.LEARNING_RATE).apply_gradients(grads)
self.sess = tf.InteractiveSession()
self.sess.run(tf.global_variables_initializer())

def _assign(self, from_name, to_name):
    from_w = tf.get_collection(tf.GraphKeys.TRAINABLE_VARIABLES, scope=from_name)
    to_w = tf.get_collection(tf.GraphKeys.TRAINABLE_VARIABLES, scope=to_name)
    for i in range(len(from_w)):
        assign_op = to_w[i].assign(from_w[i])
        self.sess.run(assign_op)

def _memorize(self, state, action, reward, new_state, dead, rnn_state):
    self.MEMORIES.append((state, action, reward, new_state, dead, rnn_state))
    if len(self.MEMORIES) > self.MEMORY_SIZE:
        self.MEMORIES.popleft()

def _select_action(self, state):
    if np.random.rand() < self.EPSILON:
        action = np.random.randint(self.OUTPUT_SIZE)
    else:
        prediction = self.sess.run(self.actor.logits, feed_dict={self.actor.X:[state]})[0]
        action = np.argmax(prediction)
    return action

def _construct_memories_and_train(self, replay):
    states = np.array([a[0] for a in replay])
    new_states = np.array([a[3] for a in replay])
    init_values = np.array([a[-1] for a in replay])
    Q = self.sess.run(self.actor_target.logits, feed_dict={self.actor.X: states,
                                                         self.actor.hidden_layer: init_values})
    Q_target = self.sess.run(self.actor_target.logits, feed_dict={self.actor_target.X: states,
                                                                self.actor_target.hidden_layer: init_values})
    grads = self.sess.run(self.grad_critic, feed_dict={self.critic.X:states, self.critic.Y:Q,
                                                         self.critic.hidden_layer: init_values})[0]
    self.sess.run(self.optimizer, feed_dict={self.actor.X:states, self.actor.critic_grad:grads,
                                             self.actor.hidden_layer: init_values})

    rewards = np.array([a[2] for a in replay]).reshape((-1, 1))
    rewards_target = self.sess.run(self.critic_target.logits,
                                   feed_dict={self.critic_target.X:new_states,self.critic_target.Y:Q_target,
                                               self.critic_target.hidden_layer: init_values})

    for i in range(len(replay)):
        if not replay[i][2]:
            rewards[i] += self.GAMMA * rewards_target[i]
    cost, _ = self.sess.run([self.critic.cost, self.critic.optimizer],
                            feed_dict={self.critic.X:states, self.critic.Y:Q, self.critic.REWARD:rewards,
                                        self.critic.hidden_layer: init_values})
    return cost

def get_state(self, t):
    window_size = self.window_size + 1
    d = t - window_size + 1
    block = self.trend[d : t + 1] if d >= 0 else -d * [self.trend[0]] + self.trend[0 : t + 1]
    res = []
    for i in range(window_size - 1):
        res.append(block[i + 1] - block[i])
    return np.array(res)

def buy(self, initial_money):
    starting_money = initial_money
    states_sell = []
    states_buy = []
    inventory = []
    state = self.get_state(0)
    init_value = np.zeros((1, 2 * self.LAYER_SIZE))
    for k in range(self.INITIAL_FEATURES.shape[0]):
        self.INITIAL_FEATURES[k,:] = state
    for t in range(0, len(self.trend) - 1, self.skip):
        if np.random.rand() < self.EPSILON:
            action = np.random.randint(self.OUTPUT_SIZE)
        else:
            action, last_state = self.sess.run([self.actor.logits,
                                               self.actor.last_state],
                                               feed_dict={self.actor.X:[self.INITIAL_FEATURES],
                                                         self.actor.hidden_layer:init_value})
            action, init_value = np.argmax(action[0]), last_state

        next_state = self.get_state(t + 1)

        if action == 1 and initial_money >= self.trend[t]:
            inventory.append(self.trend[t])
            initial_money -= self.trend[t]
```


The image displays three sequential screenshots of a Jupyter Notebook titled 'Review3.ipynb' in a Colaboratory environment. The code implements a reinforcement learning agent for a stock trading task. The agent's state is represented by a vector of features, and it chooses between two actions: buying (action 1) or selling (action 2). The environment provides price trends, and the agent's goal is to maximize profit over a series of iterations. The code includes functions for state transitions, action selection, and training. A warning at the bottom indicates that the `LSTMCell` class is deprecated in TensorFlow.

```
[ ]  
if action == 1 and initial_money >= self.trend[t]:  
    inventory.append(self.trend[t])  
    initial_money -= self.trend[t]  
    states_buy.append(t)  
    print('day %d: buy 1 unit at price %f, total balance %f' % (t, self.trend[t], initial_money))  
  
elif action == 2 and len(inventory):  
    bought_price = inventory.pop(0)  
    initial_money += self.trend[t]  
    states_sell.append(t)  
    try:  
        invest = ((close[t] - bought_price) / bought_price) * 100  
    except:  
        invest = 0  
    print('day %d, sell 1 unit at price %f, investment %f%%, total balance %f,'  
          % (t, close[t], invest, initial_money))  
  
new_state = np.append([self.get_state(t + 1)], self.INITIAL_FEATURES[:3, :], axis = 0)  
self.INITIAL_FEATURES = new_state  
invest = ((initial_money - starting_money) / starting_money) * 100  
total_gains = initial_money - starting_money  
return states_buy, states_sell, total_gains, invest  
  
def train(self, iterations, checkpoint, initial_money):  
    total_profit = 0  
    inventory = []  
    state = self.get_state(0)  
    starting_money = initial_money  
    init_value = np.zeros(1, 2 * self.LAYER_SIZE)  
    for k in range(self.INITIAL_FEATURES.shape[0]):  
        self.INITIAL_FEATURES[k, :] = state  
  
    if np.random.rand() < self.EPSILON:  
        action = np.random.randint(self.OUTPUT_SIZE)  
    else:  
        action, last_state = self.sess.run([self.actor_logits,  
                                           self.actor.last_state],  
                                           feed_dict={self.actor.X: [self.INITIAL_FEATURES],  
                                                         self.actor.hidden_layer: init_value})  
        action, init_value = np.argmax(action[0]), last_state  
  
    next_state = self.get_state(t + 1)  
  
    if action == 1 and starting_money >= self.trend[t]:  
        inventory.append(self.trend[t])  
        starting_money -= self.trend[t]  
  
    elif action == 2 and len(inventory) > 0:  
        bought_price = inventory.pop(0)  
        total_profit += self.trend[t] - bought_price  
        starting_money += self.trend[t]  
  
    invest = ((starting_money - initial_money) / initial_money)  
    new_state = np.append([self.get_state(t + 1)], self.INITIAL_FEATURES[:3, :], axis = 0)  
  
    self.memorize(self.INITIAL_FEATURES, action, invest, new_state,  
                 starting_money < initial_money, init_value[0])  
    self.INITIAL_FEATURES = new_state  
    replay = random.sample(self.MEMORIES, batch_size)  
    cost = self.construct_memories_and_train(replay)  
    self.T_COPY += 1  
    self.EPSILON = self.MIN_EPSILON + (1.0 - self.MIN_EPSILON) * np.exp(-self.DECAY_RATE * i)  
    if (i+1) % checkpoint == 0:  
        print('epoch: %d, total rewards: %f.3, cost: %f, total money: %f' % (i + 1, total_profit, cost,  
                                                                              starting_money))  
  
[ ] close = df.Close.values.tolist()  
initial_money = 10000  
window_size = 30  
skip = 1  
batch_size = 32  
agent = Agent(state_size = window_size,  
              window_size = window_size,  
              trend = close,  
              skip = skip)  
agent.train(iterations = 100, checkpoint = 5, initial_money = initial_money)  
  
WARNING:tensorflow:From <ipython-input-4-850e0890f577>:9: LSTMCell._init__ (from tensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl) is deprecated and will be  
instructions for updating:
```

```

Review3.ipynb - Colaboratory
colab.research.google.com/drive/1HN1UyE8ZaFIDYyWGSYEQnqFn6LJBHQw#scrollTo=YeVu_SDp-5H

Review3.ipynb
File Edit View Insert Runtime Tools Help All changes saved

+ Code + Text
from keras import layers, utils, metrics, models, keras_backend as backend

Instructions for updating:
Call initializer instance with the dtype argument instead of passing it to the constructor
WARNING:tensorflow:From /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/ops/rnn_cell_impl.py:962: calling Zeros._init__ (from tens
Instructions for updating:
Use keras.layers.Dense instead.
WARNING:tensorflow:From /usr/local/lib/python3.6/dist-packages/tensorflow_core/python/layers/core.py:187: Layer.apply (from tensorflow.python.ker
Instructions for updating:
Please use 'layer.call' method instead.
WARNING:tensorflow:ctensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f200f0dca80: Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon be
WARNING:tensorflow:ctensorflow.python.ops.rnn_cell_impl.LSTMCell object at 0x7f20069a0b80: Using a concatenated state is slower and will soon be
epoch: 5, total rewards: -24.010254, cost: 0.077577, total money: 2066.029540
epoch: 10, total rewards: -79.669923, cost: 0.152671, total money: 2110.980181
epoch: 15, total rewards: 647.560547, cost: 0.066494, total money: 7927.700439
epoch: 20, total rewards: 115.250007, cost: 0.226919, total money: 6032.270027
epoch: 25, total rewards: 1429.950195, cost: 0.200271, total money: 10026.690185
epoch: 30, total rewards: 1031.970338, cost: 0.190580, total money: 11031.970338
epoch: 35, total rewards: -249.630003, cost: 0.118293, total money: 4305.279989
epoch: 40, total rewards: 1536.289910, cost: 0.095909, total money: 7509.049920
epoch: 45, total rewards: -110.669673, cost: 0.076333, total money: 23.380249
epoch: 50, total rewards: 600.840704, cost: 0.107810, total money: 3910.050665
epoch: 55, total rewards: 407.709960, cost: 0.089295, total money: 2615.559936
epoch: 60, total rewards: -561.789797, cost: 0.091912, total money: 5300.470213
epoch: 65, total rewards: -44.699708, cost: 0.068624, total money: 7207.080243
epoch: 70, total rewards: 1112.500124, cost: 0.116068, total money: 5823.339967
epoch: 75, total rewards: 663.139769, cost: 0.118756, total money: 2672.409789
epoch: 80, total rewards: 523.699702, cost: 0.108128, total money: 10523.699702
epoch: 85, total rewards: 1074.719236, cost: 0.371936, total money: 6996.699216
epoch: 90, total rewards: -306.440064, cost: 0.048781, total money: 8337.429931
epoch: 95, total rewards: 166.040042, cost: 0.029822, total money: 10166.040042
epoch: 100, total rewards: 538.850957, cost: 0.080618, total money: 9182.720952

[ ] states_buy, states_sell, total_gains, invest = agent.buy(initial_money = initial_money)

day 0: buy 1 unit at price 1178.979980, total balance 8821.020020

```

```

epoch: 90, total rewards: -306.440064, cost: 0.048781, total money: 8337.429931
epoch: 95, total rewards: 166.040042, cost: 0.029822, total money: 10166.040042
epoch: 100, total rewards: 538.850957, cost: 0.080618, total money: 9182.720952

[ ] states_buy, states_sell, total_gains, invest = agent.buy(initial_money = initial_money)

day 0: buy 1 unit at price 1178.979980, total balance 8821.020020
day 2: sell 1 unit at price 1138.849976, investment -3.403790 %, total balance 9959.869996,
day 8: buy 1 unit at price 1117.949951, total balance 7725.460084
day 11, sell 1 unit at price 1036.229980, investment -7.186105 %, total balance 8761.690064,
day 12: buy 1 unit at price 1053.050049, total balance 7708.640015
day 13, sell 1 unit at price 1042.219971, investment -6.774005 %, total balance 8750.859986,
day 17, sell 1 unit at price 1078.719971, investment 2.437674 %, total balance 9829.579957,
day 19: buy 1 unit at price 1088.770020, total balance 8740.809937
day 20, sell 1 unit at price 1085.349976, investment -0.314120 %, total balance 9826.159913,
day 22: buy 1 unit at price 1103.599976, total balance 8722.559937
day 23, sell 1 unit at price 1102.329956, investment -0.115080 %, total balance 9824.889893,
day 37: buy 1 unit at price 1144.479980, total balance 8684.409913
day 38: buy 1 unit at price 1144.209961, total balance 7540.199952
day 39: buy 1 unit at price 1144.900024, total balance 6395.299928
day 40, sell 1 unit at price 1150.330066, investment 0.864567 %, total balance 7545.639804,
day 41: buy 1 unit at price 1153.579956, total balance 6392.059938
day 42: buy 1 unit at price 1146.349976, total balance 5245.709962
day 43: buy 1 unit at price 1146.329956, total balance 4099.389006
day 44: buy 1 unit at price 1130.099976, total balance 2969.280030
day 45, sell 1 unit at price 1138.069946, investment -0.536016 %, total balance 4107.349976,
day 46, sell 1 unit at price 1146.209961, investment 0.114415 %, total balance 5253.559937,
day 47: buy 1 unit at price 1137.810059, total balance 4115.749878
day 48, sell 1 unit at price 1132.119955, investment -1.860292 %, total balance 5247.869873,
day 49, sell 1 unit at price 1250.410034, total balance 5258.869873
day 50: buy 1 unit at price 1239.410034, total balance 5258.869873
day 51, sell 1 unit at price 1225.140015, investment 6.874989 %, total balance 6484.009888,
day 52, sell 1 unit at price 1216.680054, investment 7.661276 %, total balance 7700.689942,
day 53, sell 1 unit at price 1209.010010, investment 6.257631 %, total balance 8909.699952,
day 54, sell 1 unit at price 1193.989990, investment -3.664650 %, total balance 10103.689942,
day 58: buy 1 unit at price 1204.800049, total balance 8909.889893

```


C. Predicting which stock to buy

The image displays three sequential screenshots of a Jupyter Notebook environment, showing the execution of Python code for financial data analysis. The code uses libraries like pandas, matplotlib, and seaborn to process stock data, calculate returns and volatilities, and create a joint plot.

Code Snippets:

```

import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import pandas.util.testing as tm
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
sns.set()

[ ] directory = ''
ori_name = ['ACN.csv', 'AMZN.csv', 'CTSH.csv', 'FB.csv', 'GOOG.csv',
            'IBM.csv', 'INFY.csv', 'MSFT.csv', 'TCS.NS.csv', 'WIT.csv']
stocks = [directory + s for s in ori_name]

[ ] dfs = [pd.read_csv(s)[['Date', 'Close']] for s in stocks]

[ ] from functools import reduce
data = reduce(lambda left, right: pd.merge(left, right, on='Date'), dfs).iloc[:, 1:]
data.head()

[ ] returns = data.pct_change()
mean_daily_returns = returns.mean()
volatilities = returns.std()

[ ] mean_daily_returns * 252

Close_x    0.101293
Close_y    0.321788
Close_x   -0.080167
Close_y    0.219622
Close_x    0.244607
Close_y   -0.079293
Close_x   -0.074989
Close_y    0.462374
Close_x   -0.051113
Close_y   -0.407720
dtype: float64

[ ] volatilities * 252

Close_x    5.916300
Close_y    5.047147
Close_x    7.121601
Close_y    6.386430
Close_x    5.802138
Close_y    5.859486
Close_x    6.763885
Close_y    6.347253
Close_x    5.381582
Close_y    5.015238
dtype: float64

[ ] combine = pd.DataFrame({'returns': mean_daily_returns * 252,
                           'volatility': volatilities * 252})

[ ] g = sns.jointplot("volatility", "returns", data=combine, kind="reg", height=7)

for i in range(combine.shape[0]):
    plt.annotate(ori_name[i].replace('.csv',''), (combine.iloc[i, 1], combine.iloc[i, 0]))

plt.text(0, -1.5, 'SELL', fontsize=25)
plt.text(0, 1.0, 'BUY', fontsize=25)

plt.show()

```

Table 1: Sample Data from the Notebook

	Close_x	Close_y	Close_x	Close_y	Close_x	Close_y	Close_x	Close_y	Close_x	Close_y
0	178.330002	1869.000000	59.439999	185.300003	1162.300049	134.320007	10.17	128.070007	2095.449951	4.47
1	178.539993	1858.969971	59.990002	182.720001	1138.849976	135.119995	10.20	126.220001	2143.949951	4.58
2	179.570007	1857.520020	61.000000	184.820007	1149.630005	136.449997	10.18	126.900002	2109.750000	4.48
3	180.389999	1859.680054	61.500000	185.320007	1151.420044	136.350006	10.22	127.669998	2081.750000	4.46
4	178.270004	1815.479980	61.080002	180.869995	1140.770020	132.389999	10.16	126.180000	2054.050049	4.42

Table 2: Calculated Returns and Volatilities

	Close_x	Close_y	Close_x	Close_y	Close_x	Close_y	Close_x	Close_y	Close_x	Close_y
	0.101293	0.321788	-0.080167	0.219622	0.244607	-0.079293	-0.074989	0.462374	-0.051113	-0.407720
	5.916300	5.047147	7.121601	6.386430	5.802138	5.859486	6.763885	6.347253	5.381582	5.015238

Figure: A joint plot showing the relationship between volatility and returns. The plot includes a regression line and a shaded area representing the confidence interval. Annotations 'BUY' and 'SELL' are placed on the plot based on the return values.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS:

A. Predicting the price of the stock:

The stock prices of NIFTY 50 was downloaded from the NSE site and we forecasted the prices of the stocks for the upcoming month as illustrated in Fig. 7.1.

Figure 7.1

B. Predicting when to buy and sell shares:

With this code we found out the buy-sell points of the stock. We used the stock value of google to make this prediction. We gave the user a total of 10,000 units worth currency to invest in the stocks. After all the selling and buying is done we calculate the overall profits.

epoch: 5, total rewards: -24.010254.3, cost: 0.077557, total money: 2066.029540
 epoch: 10, total rewards: -79.669923.3, cost: 0.152671, total money: 2110.980101
 epoch: 15, total rewards: 647.560547.3, cost: 0.066494, total money: 7927.700439
 epoch: 20, total rewards: 115.250007.3, cost: 0.226919, total money: 6032.270027
 epoch: 25, total rewards: 1429.950195.3, cost: 0.200271, total money: 10026.690185
 epoch: 30, total rewards: 1031.970338.3, cost: 0.190580, total money: 11031.970338
 epoch: 35, total rewards: -249.630003.3, cost: 0.118293, total money: 4305.279909
 epoch: 40, total rewards: 1536.289910.3, cost: 0.095009, total money: 7509.049920
 epoch: 45, total rewards: -110.669677.3, cost: 0.076333, total money: 23.380249
 epoch: 50, total rewards: 600.840704.3, cost: 0.107810, total money: 3910.050665
 epoch: 55, total rewards: 407.709960.3, cost: 0.089295, total money: 2615.559936
 epoch: 60, total rewards: -561.789797.3, cost: 0.091912, total money: 5390.470213
 epoch: 65, total rewards: -44.699708.3, cost: 0.068624, total money: 7207.000243
 epoch: 70, total rewards: 1112.500124.3, cost: 0.116068, total money: 5823.339967
 epoch: 75, total rewards: 663.139769.3, cost: 0.118758, total money: 2672.409789

epoch: 80, total rewards: 523.699702.3, cost: 0.108128, total money: 10523.699702
epoch: 85, total rewards: 1074.719236.3, cost: 0.371936, total money: 6996.699216
epoch: 90, total rewards: -306.440064.3, cost: 0.048781, total money: 8337.429931
epoch: 95, total rewards: 166.040042.3, cost: 0.029822, total money: 10166.040042
epoch: 100, total rewards: 538.850957.3, cost: 0.080618, total money: 9182.720952

day 0: buy 1 unit at price 1178.979980, total balance 8821.020020
day 2, sell 1 unit at price 1138.849976, investment -3.403790 %, total balance 9959.869996,
day 8: buy 1 unit at price 1116.459961, total balance 8843.410035
day 9: buy 1 unit at price 1117.949951, total balance 7725.460084
day 11, sell 1 unit at price 1036.229980, investment -7.186105 %, total balance 8761.690064,
day 12: buy 1 unit at price 1053.050049, total balance 7708.640015
day 13, sell 1 unit at price 1042.219971, investment -6.774005 %, total balance 8750.859986,
day 17, sell 1 unit at price 1078.719971, investment 2.437674 %, total balance 9829.579957,
day 19: buy 1 unit at price 1088.770020, total balance 8740.809937
day 20, sell 1 unit at price 1085.349976, investment -0.314120 %, total balance 9826.159913,
day 22: buy 1 unit at price 1103.599976, total balance 8722.559937
day 23, sell 1 unit at price 1102.329956, investment -0.115080 %, total balance 9824.889893,
day 37: buy 1 unit at price 1140.479980, total balance 8684.409913
day 38: buy 1 unit at price 1144.209961, total balance 7540.199952
day 39: buy 1 unit at price 1144.900024, total balance 6395.299928
day 40, sell 1 unit at price 1150.339966, investment 0.864547 %, total balance 7545.639894,
day 41: buy 1 unit at price 1153.579956, total balance 6392.059938
day 42: buy 1 unit at price 1146.349976, total balance 5245.709962
day 43: buy 1 unit at price 1146.329956, total balance 4099.380006
day 44: buy 1 unit at price 1130.099976, total balance 2969.280030
day 45, sell 1 unit at price 1138.069946, investment -0.536616 %, total balance 4107.349976,
day 46, sell 1 unit at price 1146.209961, investment 0.114415 %, total balance 5253.559937,
day 47: buy 1 unit at price 1137.810059, total balance 4115.749878
day 48, sell 1 unit at price 1132.119995, investment -1.860292 %, total balance 5247.869873,
day 49, sell 1 unit at price 1250.410034, investment 9.077512 %, total balance 6498.279907,
day 50: buy 1 unit at price 1239.410034, total balance 5258.869873
day 51, sell 1 unit at price 1225.140015, investment 6.874989 %, total balance 6484.009888,
day 52, sell 1 unit at price 1216.680054, investment 7.661276 %, total balance 7700.689942,
day 53, sell 1 unit at price 1209.010010, investment 6.257631 %, total balance 8909.699952,
day 54, sell 1 unit at price 1193.989990, investment -3.664650 %, total balance 10103.689942,
day 58: buy 1 unit at price 1204.800049, total balance 8898.889893
day 59, sell 1 unit at price 1188.010010, investment -1.393595 %, total balance 10086.899903,
day 60: buy 1 unit at price 1174.709961, total balance 8912.189942
day 61, sell 1 unit at price 1197.270020, investment 1.920479 %, total balance 10109.459962,
day 65: buy 1 unit at price 1198.449951, total balance 8911.010011
day 66: buy 1 unit at price 1182.689941, total balance 7728.320070
day 67, sell 1 unit at price 1191.250000, investment -0.600772 %, total balance 8919.570070,
day 68, sell 1 unit at price 1189.530029, investment 0.578350 %, total balance 10109.100099,
day 69: buy 1 unit at price 1151.290039, total balance 8957.810060
day 71, sell 1 unit at price 1167.839966, investment 1.437512 %, total balance 10125.650026,
day 76: buy 1 unit at price 1181.410034, total balance 8944.239992
day 78, sell 1 unit at price 1204.930054, investment 1.990843 %, total balance 10149.170046,
day 81: buy 1 unit at price 1220.170044, total balance 8929.000002
day 82, sell 1 unit at price 1234.250000, investment 1.153934 %, total balance 10163.250002,
day 86: buy 1 unit at price 1232.410034, total balance 8930.839968
day 88, sell 1 unit at price 1229.930054, investment -0.201230 %, total balance 10160.770022,
day 91: buy 1 unit at price 1246.520020, total balance 8914.250002
day 93, sell 1 unit at price 1225.089966, investment -1.719191 %, total balance 10139.339968,
day 95: buy 1 unit at price 1205.099976, total balance 8934.239992
day 97, sell 1 unit at price 1187.829956, investment -1.433078 %, total balance 10122.069948,
day 103: buy 1 unit at price 1215.449951, total balance 8906.619997
day 104, sell 1 unit at price 1217.140015, investment 0.139048 %, total balance 10123.760012,
day 105: buy 1 unit at price 1243.010010, total balance 8880.750002

day 106, sell 1 unit at price 1243.640015, investment 0.050684 %, total balance 10124.390017,
day 114: buy 1 unit at price 1290.000000, total balance 8834.390017
day 115, sell 1 unit at price 1262.619995, investment -2.122481 %, total balance 10097.010012,
day 119: buy 1 unit at price 1291.369995, total balance 8805.640017
day 120, sell 1 unit at price 1292.030029, investment 0.051111 %, total balance 10097.670046,
day 128: buy 1 unit at price 1334.869995, total balance 8762.800051
day 129: buy 1 unit at price 1320.699951, total balance 7442.100100
day 130, sell 1 unit at price 1315.459961, investment -1.454077 %, total balance 8757.560061,
day 134: buy 1 unit at price 1306.689941, total balance 7450.870120
day 137, sell 1 unit at price 1304.959961, investment -1.191792 %, total balance 8755.830081,
day 138: buy 1 unit at price 1289.920044, total balance 7465.910037
day 143: buy 1 unit at price 1343.560059, total balance 6122.349978
day 144, sell 1 unit at price 1344.660034, investment 2.905823 %, total balance 7467.010012,
day 145: buy 1 unit at price 1345.020020, total balance 6121.989992
day 146, sell 1 unit at price 1350.270020, investment 4.678583 %, total balance 7472.260012,
day 148, sell 1 unit at price 1361.170044, investment 1.310696 %, total balance 8833.430056,
day 149: buy 1 unit at price 1355.119995, total balance 7478.310061
day 150, sell 1 unit at price 1352.619995, investment 0.565045 %, total balance 8830.930056,
day 151, sell 1 unit at price 1356.040039, investment 0.067894 %, total balance 10186.970095,
day 153: buy 1 unit at price 1348.839966, total balance 8838.130129
day 154, sell 1 unit at price 1343.560059, investment -0.391441 %, total balance 10181.690188,
day 167: buy 1 unit at price 1430.880005, total balance 8750.810183
day 169, sell 1 unit at price 1451.699951, investment 1.455045 %, total balance 10202.510134,
day 171: buy 1 unit at price 1484.400024, total balance 8718.110110
day 172: buy 1 unit at price 1485.949951, total balance 7232.160159
day 173, sell 1 unit at price 1486.650024, investment 0.151576 %, total balance 8718.810183,
day 174, sell 1 unit at price 1466.709961, investment -1.294794 %, total balance 10185.520144,
day 182: buy 1 unit at price 1448.229980, total balance 8737.290164
day 183, sell 1 unit at price 1476.229980, investment 1.933395 %, total balance 10213.520144,
day 184: buy 1 unit at price 1479.229980, total balance 8734.290164
day 185, sell 1 unit at price 1508.680054, investment 1.990906 %, total balance 10242.970218,
day 186: buy 1 unit at price 1508.790039, total balance 8734.180179
day 189, sell 1 unit at price 1520.739990, investment 0.792022 %, total balance 10254.920169,
day 192: buy 1 unit at price 1518.150024, total balance 8736.770145
day 193, sell 1 unit at price 1485.109985, investment -2.176336 %, total balance 10221.880130,
day 197: buy 1 unit at price 1318.089966, total balance 8903.790164
day 198, sell 1 unit at price 1339.329956, investment 1.611422 %, total balance 10243.120120,
day 199: buy 1 unit at price 1389.109985, total balance 8854.010135
day 200, sell 1 unit at price 1341.390015, investment -3.435291 %, total balance 10195.400150,
day 205: buy 1 unit at price 1280.390015, total balance 8915.010135
day 206, sell 1 unit at price 1215.410034, investment -5.075015 %, total balance 10130.420169,
day 215: buy 1 unit at price 1134.459961, total balance 8995.960208
day 216, sell 1 unit at price 1102.489990, investment -2.818078 %, total balance 10098.450198,
day 223: buy 1 unit at price 1097.880005, total balance 9000.570193
day 224: buy 1 unit at price 1186.920044, total balance 7813.650149
day 225, sell 1 unit at price 1186.510010, investment 8.072832 %, total balance 9000.160159,
day 227, sell 1 unit at price 1211.449951, investment 2.066686 %, total balance 10211.610110,
day 247: buy 1 unit at price 1388.369995, total balance 8823.240115
day 248, sell 1 unit at price 1403.260010, investment 1.072482 %, total balance 10226.500125,
day 249: buy 1 unit at price 1375.739990, total balance 8850.760135
day 250, sell 1 unit at price 1349.329956, investment -1.919697 %, total balance 10200.090091,

Figure 7.2

C. Predicting which stock to buy:

In this code we found out in which company we should invest and the volatility of the stocks of that company. We used the datasets of Cognizant, IBM, TCS, Infosys, Accenture, Wipro, Facebook, Google, Amazon and Microsoft.

Figure 7.3

IV. SUMMARY

From this project I have been able to form a structure about a product I wish to develop in the future. In this project I have developed an easy to use website which will help its customers to invest in cryptocurrencies and shares. In this project I have used coinbase as a platform to invest in BTC. In the future this product can be made fully functional by improving the website. This product will also predict the following things:

1. The fluctuation of price of the share value of a company using a hybrid LSTM seq2seq algorithm.
2. When to invest and sell shares using an actor-critic recurrent agent (deep learning).
3. Which company to invest in and the risk related to it.

The future scope is to develop even more efficient algorithms to ensure more profits for the customers. The product will ensure its income by charging a commission from the profit incurred by the customers. The advantage of using this product over others will be that if a customer incurs a loss, no commission will be charged from him/her.

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